

3-Hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as a spectrophotometric reagent for the micro-determination of tin

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Manuscript received 02 July 2010, revised 11 May 2011, accepted 26 May 2011

Abstract : A simple, rapid, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method for the determination of micro-amounts of tin has been worked out employing 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran as a complexing ligand in acidic medium. The complex is extractable into carbon tetrachloride and shows maximum absorbance at 424 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.0 to 3.04 $\mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}}/\text{ml}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are $4.87 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0024 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}}/\text{cm}^2$ at 424 nm respectively. The method is free from interference of large number of anions/complexing agents and cations. The method has been satisfactorily applied to the analysis of tin in various samples including tin can and gun metal.

Keywords : Tin, 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, extraction, spectrophotometric.

Introduction

In the literature there are numerous analytical methods for the measurement of tin which are based on sophisticated instruments. These include decompressed micro-chromatographic column¹, inductive coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry²⁻⁴, molecular emission cavity analysis⁵, electro-thermal atomic absorption spectrometry⁶ and flow injection hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry⁷. Such methods are highly sensitive, but generally tedious and prone to suffer from serious interferences from other elements. In contrast spectrophotometric methods are more preferred because of their simplicity and speed in routine analysis. A large number of reagents such as 5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinol⁸, dimethylglyoxime⁹, 2-(5-nitro-2-pyridylazo)-5-[N-n-propyl-N-(3-sulphopropyl)amino-phenol]¹⁰, potassium ethyl xanthate¹¹, ferron¹², pyrocatechol violet^{13,14}, isoamyl xanthate¹⁵ and diacetylmonoxime-p-hydroxy-benzoyl-hyrazone¹⁶ have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of tin. Among these many reagents^{8,11-15} are

non selective as they suffer from the interference from Mo, Co, Bi, Zr, W, Ti, Sb, tartrate, oxalate, and citrate while some of them require time for full colour development^{10,11,14}. With a view to overcome such difficulties, a chromone derivative 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran¹⁷ has been used for complexation and spectrophotometric determination of trace amount of tin after extraction of the yellow coloured complex into carbon tetrachloride.

Experimental

Apparatus : A (model-140-02, Shimadzu) with 10 mm quartz cells was used for the routine absorbance measurements and spectral studies. The IR spectra and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 1710 FTIR spectrometer over the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} and Bruker (300 MHz) spectrometer, respectively.

Reagents and solutions : All the chemicals used were of analytical grade with highest purity. Carbon tetrachloride was distilled and the fraction distilling at 77 °C was

used for Sn^{II}-HPMPPB complex extraction.

Tin and other metals ions standard solution : The standard stock solution (250 ml) of Sn^{II} containing 1 mg ml⁻¹ of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed amount (0.475 g) of SnCl₂·H₂O (AR, Reidel) in 20 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid, diluting with deionize water up to the mark and standardized gravimetrically¹⁸. Lower concentration at μg ml⁻¹ level was prepared by suitable dilution of this solution containing 0.5 mol L⁻¹ HCl as final acidity. The containers of the tin solution were wrapped with carbon paper and kept in dark place. Stock solutions of other metal ions were prepared at mg ml⁻¹ level by dissolving their soluble salts in deionized water or dilute acid and suitably diluted to give μg ml⁻¹ level concentration of the respective metal ions. For anions, respective sodium and potassium salts were dissolved.

HPMPPB solution : 3-Hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPMPPB; m.p. 221–224 °C) was synthesized by the literature method¹⁷ and dissolved in acetone to give 0.3% (m/v) solution. The molecular formula of HPMPPB is C₂₅H₁₈O₄N₂ and its structure is given below :

HPMPPB

Preparations of samples for analysis : The synthetic samples were prepared by mixing tin solution with solutions of various metal ions in suitable proportions so as to give the composition as shown in Table 1.

Gun metal : A weighed sample of gun metal (0.2 g) was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 2–4 ml of concentrated nitric acid by heating and the volume was made up to 100 ml in a volumetric flask. 10 ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml to get a working solution of low concentration. An aliquot of resulting

Table 1. Analysis of samples by the proposed method

Sample composition	Sn added (μg)	Sn found** (μg)
Matrix*		
Ta (0.1), Au (0.05), Ru (0.001)	6	6.08
U (1), Th (0.01), Se (3), Be (2)	8	7.96
As (5), Ag (0.5), Cu (1), Cd (2)	10	9.92
Mo (0.005), Ti (0.05), Mn (2) ^a	12	12.0
Ca (2), Ir (0.007), Al (2)	11	11.04
Zr (0.05), W (0.003), Cr (0.1) ^b	5	5.17
Cu (1.199), Zn (0.416), Pb (0.333) ^{c1}	20	19.76
Cu (0.203), Pb (0.104), Ni (0.00293), Fe (0.0097) ^{c2,d}	15	15.08
Cu (0.103), Sb (0.011) ^{c3}	14	14.0
Gun metal	4.9% ^e	4.45%
Tin can ^f	–	0.14%

*Amount of metal ion shown in parentheses is in m% **Average of triplicate analyses. ^aIn presence of 0.5 ml of H₂O₂ [30% (m/v)]. ^bIn presence of 15 mg of phosphate. ^{c1,c2,c3}Correspond to bertheir alloy, ceco alloy and chinese speculum alloy, respectively. ^dIn the presence of 5 mg ascorbic acid. ^eCertified value and confirmed by SnO₂ method. ^fRef. 11.

sample solution was analyzed by the proposed method.

Tin can : A weighed sample (0.6 g) of tin can, taken in a 100 ml beaker, was heated gently with 5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The sample was dissolved completely by adding 5–10 ml of distilled water and heating until the volume was reduced to 2–5 ml. After cooling, the volume of the solution was made up to 25 ml and suitable portions of the sample solution were analyzed for tin content.

Procedure : To 1 ml aliquot of the sample solution containing ≤ 30.4 μg Sn^{II} in 0.5 M hydrochloric acid, were added 0.9–2.8 ml of 0.3% 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPMPPB) reagent in acetone and enough deionized water to raise the aqueous volume to 10 ml in a 125 ml separatory funnel. The contents were mixed well and equilibrated with an equal volume (10 ml) of carbon tetrachloride, releasing the pressure by removing the stopper occasionally, once for 40 s. The layers were allowed to separate and the yellow coloured solvent layer was passed through Whatman filter paper (No. 41, 9 cm diameter, pretreated with carbon tetrachloride) to remove water droplets if any and collected the solvent layer in to a 10 ml measuring flask. The absorbance of the organic extract was then measured at 424 nm against similarly

treated reagent blank. The amount of Sn^{II} was determined from the calibration curve.

Modifications of the method for the samples containing Fe^{III} , Nb^{V} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Bi^{III} and Ti^{IV} : Under the optimum conditions of the method as discussed, the sample containing the metal ions Fe^{III} , Nb^{V} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Bi^{III} and Ti^{IV} were found to give coloured extracts with high absorbance value. Fe^{III} and V^{V} show red colour whereas Nb^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Bi^{III} and Ti^{IV} give dark yellow colour to the solvent phase. The co-extraction of these metals could be prevented by making use of suitable masking agents i.e. for 0.2 mg of Fe^{III} and 0.1 mg of V^{V} , 75 mg ascorbic acid; for 1 mg of Nb^{V} , 1 mg o.s.alate; for 0.03 mg of Mo^{VI} and 0.4 mg of Ti^{IV} , 0.5 ml of 30% H_2O_2 (w/v); for 0.2 mg of W^{VI} and 0.3 mg of Zr^{IV} , 13 mg sodium phosphate and for 3 mg of Bi^{III} , 100 mg thiourea prior to the addition of HPMPPB in 10 ml aqueous volume.

Results and discussion

It has been observed that tin(II) forms a yellow coloured complex with HPMPPB reagent in acidic medium which was found to be extractable into carbon tetrachloride. The absorption spectrum of the Sn^{II} -HPMPPB complex in carbon tetrachloride along with that of blank is shown in Fig. 1. The reagent blank shows a strong absorption at 400 nm which, however, decreases sharply on

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of Sn^{II} -HPMPPB complex into carbon tetrachloride. (A) $1.0 \mu\text{g Sn}^{\text{II}} \text{ ml}^{-1}$ measured against reagent blank, (B) reagent blank measured against carbon tetrachloride.

going towards longer wavelength and becomes negligibly small at 421 nm or beyond. The complex shows a broad absorption band between 421–427 nm, where the reagent blank has minimum absorbance therefore, all the measurements were carried out at 424 nm.

Effect of varying experimental condition: The influence of different parameters on the extraction of Sn^{II} -HPMPPB complex were optimized and the results of these parameters are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of various parameters on the absorbance of Sn^{II} -HPMPPB complex

HCl ^a (M)	0.01	0.014	0.018	0.02–0.08	0.1
Absorbance	0.290	0.350	0.380	0.410	0.360
HPMPPB ^b (ml)	0.4	0.6	0.8	0.9–2.8	3.0
Absorbance	0.260	0.340	0.390	0.410	0.370
Equilibration time ^c (s)	5	10	15	20–95	100
Absorbance	0.280	0.340	0.380	0.410	0.370

Conditions : ^a $\text{Sn}^{\text{II}} = 10 \mu\text{g}$; HCl = variable; HPMPPB (0.3% (m/v) in acetone) = 1.3 ml; aqueous volume = solvent volume = 10 ml; solvent = carbon tetrachloride; equilibration time = 40 s; $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 424 \text{ nm}$, ^bHCl = 0.05 M; other conditions being the same as in (a) except for the variation in HPMPPB concentration; also ^b = 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPMPPB), ^c0.3% HPMPPB in acetone = 1.3 ml; other conditions being the same as in (b) except for the variation in equilibration time.

Effect of concentration of HCl: The absorbance of the complex was found to increase with the increase in hydrochloric acid concentration of the aqueous phase, but it remains constant upto 0.08 M and then began to decrease with further increase in acidity. So the 0.05 M HCl concentration was considered for further experiments.

Choice of solvent: Tin(II) formed a yellow complex with HPMPPB in HCl medium which was extracted by various organic solvents namely carbon tetrachloride, 1,2-dichloroethane, chloroform, dichloromethane, toluene, isoamylacetate, ethyl acetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl alcohol and *n*-butanol in the decreasing order of the absorbance. As carbon tetrachloride shows the maximum and stable absorbance, so it was chosen as extractant for the metal complex under study.

Effect of reagent concentration: The effect of concentration of 3-hydroxy-2-[1'-phenyl-3'-(4''-methoxyphenyl)-4'-pyrazoyl]-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (HPMPPB 0.3% in acetone) on the absorbance of the complex has been stud-

ied. It was found to be nil in the absence of the reagent and increased with the corresponding increase in the reagent concentration. For 0.9–2.8 ml of the reagent, the complex showed maximum absorbance thereafter it started to decrease. Therefore, 1.3 ml of the reagent was used for achieving maximum absorbance.

Effect of equilibration time : When the complex was equilibrated for 4 s with carbon tetrachloride, the absorbance was 0.260, which increases with equilibration time of 20 s. The absorbance of the complex was maximum and constant for the contact time 20–95 s. Therefore, 40 s equilibration time has been taken for attaining maximum absorbance.

Beer's law obedience, stability and other statistical parameters : The complex was stable for 5 h giving a Beer's law range 0.0–3.04 Sn^{II}/ml at λ_{\max} 424 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the complex at 424 nm are $4.87 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0024 \mu\text{g Sn cm}^{-2}$, respectively under optimum conditions of the procedure.

Stoichiometry of the complex : The ratio of tin(II)-HPMPPB in the extracted species was determined using their equimolar solution ($8.425 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) at two different wavelengths 424 and 440 nm by Job's method (Fig. 2) of continuous variations as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper for a two-phase system^{19,20}. The sharp break in the curves indicates a metal-to-ligand ratio of 1 : 2 in the extracted species. This was further supported by the mole

Fig. 2. Job's method of continuous variations of Sn^{II} and HPMPPB. curve (A) 424 nm and curve (B) 440 nm.

ratio method²¹ (Fig. 3) by taking the concentration of Sn^{II} as $4.218 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and measuring the absorbance again at two wavelengths 424 and 440 nm under the optimum conditions of the procedure.

Fig. 3. Mole ratio method of HPMPPB and Sn^{II}. Curve (A) 424 and Curve (B) 440 nm.

For further conformation towards the structure of the complex, it was synthesized by the reaction of SnCl₂ and HPMPPB in 1 : 2 molar ratios. Exactly 0.113 g SnCl₂·2H₂O (AR, Reidel) (0.5 mmol) was dissolved in minimum amounts of hydrochloric acid and 0.394 g HPMPPB (1 mmol) in acetone separately. Two solutions were mixed and stirred for 5–10 min after which a yellow solid product separated out. The product was filtered on a Buckner funnel and was washed with water. The yellow precipitate was then dissolved in warm carbon tetrachloride, filtered and kept on a water bath to remove to the solvent. The last traces of the solvent were removed under reduced pressure resulting in fine yellow product. The complex is yellow in colour, soluble in common organic solvents such as CCl₄, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂ etc., however, insoluble in acetone.

In IR spectrum of HPMPPB¹⁷ a band appears at $\sim 1618 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching vibration. However, the spectrum of the complex shows a band at $\sim 1612 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to stretching vibration of carbonyl $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ group coordinated to tin. This small decrease in value of carbonyl stretching vibration indicates the coordination of carbonyl oxygen of HPMPPB to tin.

A band observed at $\sim 3440 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ in the HPMPPB¹⁷ is absent in the IR spectrum of the complex

indicating its deprotonation. The appearance of new band at about 600 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ stretching in the complex²². The IR spectrum of the tin complex suggests monobasic bidentate nature of HPMPPB. The ^1H NMR of the complex shows a number peaks in the region δ 8.50 to 6.25 ppm due to different types of phenyl protons as observed in HPMPPB¹⁷.

On the basis of the above mentioned result, the most probable structure of the tin(II)-HPMPPB complex is given as under :

Effect of diverse ions : Under optimum conditions of the procedure in 10 ml aqueous volume, the tolerance limits for different foreign ions were determined for 10 μg of tin. Chloride, iodide, nitrate, thiourea, sulphate and sulphosalicylic acid (100 mg each); bromide and carbonate (80 mg each); ascorbic acid (75 mg); sulphite (70 mg); thiocyanate (50 mg); acetate (37 mg); phosphate (13 mg); EDTA disodium salt (12 mg); citrate (10 mg); tartrate (8 mg); dithionite (2 mg); fluoride and oxalate (1 mg each); glycerol (1 ml) and H_2O_2 (30%, m/v) (0.5 ml) did not affect the determination.

Among the cations : Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mg^{II} , Hg^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Ca^{II} , As^{III} , Al^{III} and Se^{IV} (10 mg each); Ba^{II} (8 mg); Ce^{IV} (7 mg); Be^{II} , Sr^{IV} and U^{VI} (5 mg each); Cu^{II} , Re^{VII} , Os^{VIII} and Ag^{I} (3 mg each); Cr^{VI} (1.5 mg); Ir^{III} (1 mg); Th^{IV} and Ta^{V} (0.5 mg each); Au^{III} (0.2 mg); Ru^{III} , Pt^{IV} and Pd^{II} (0.1 mg each) and Sb^{III} (0.02 mg) did not affect the absorbance value. Fe^{III} , Nb^{V} , V^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV} and Bi^{III} did not interfere in the presence of respective masking agents as described under modification of the procedure.

Applications of the method :

For the determination of micro-amounts of tin, the proposed method is simple, rapid, sensitive and selective and free from the interference of a large number of diverse ions. Therefore, the procedure assumes in view of the scarcity of better methods for determining tin. The wide applicability of the method is tested by the analysis of bertheir, ceco and chinese speculum alloys (Table 1). The method is also applicable for the determination of tin in gun metal and tin can samples with satisfactory results.

The high reproducibility of the method is tested by performing several sets of experiments while keeping the same amount of tin metal ions in each set.

Acknowledgement

Our sincere thanks are due to Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra and Bhaskaracharya College of Applied Sciences (University of Delhi) for providing the necessary facilities.

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